

CERTAINTY SU's DMP

Version 0

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for ESM and observational data created at the Stockholm University is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

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Grant

CERTAINTY

Researchers

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Organizations

U. Stockholm, Sweden

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: CERTAINTY SU's DMP

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for ESM and observational data created at the Stockholm University is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

Researchers:

Ilona Riipinen (orcid:0000-0001-9085-2319)

Thorsten Mauritsen (orcid:0000-0003-1418-4077)

Radovan Krejci (orcid:0000-0002-9384-9702)

Organizations:

U. Stockholm, Sweden

Contact: Anca Hienola

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission|EC

Grants: CERTAINTY

Project: CERTAINTY

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Observational data sets on aerosol number size distributions and meteorological parameters

Field stations (ACTRIS and additional campaign-wise data)

Template: Horizon Europe

Type: Dataset

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Aerosol number size distributions, chemical composition and meteorological parameters

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1 GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study processes, interpret observations, and constrain effects of extreme weather on aerosol populations.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ACTRIS and specific measurement campaigns.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education

Project partners

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

We offer descriptive metadata that enriches data or information resources with detailed information about their content, context, and structure, thereby improving their findability and practical use.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

OAI-PMH

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

ACTRIS

<https://dc.actris.nilu.no/>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards

- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Observational data on aerosol number size distribution and composition

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes. However, we will not have closed datasets

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

The methodology that ACTRIS is following

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles and also with the input data.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Radovan Krejci (orcid:0000-0002-9384-9702)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage

- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management

Modeling data from ICON

Model outputs fields related to experiments on extreme precipitation and aerosol.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

5 TB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

<https://www.icon-model.org/>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Project partners.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

Follows repository standards

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

TBA

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Collaboration with other Projects

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Thorsten Mauritsen (orcid:0000-0003-1418-4077)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

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ESM simulation data

Nudged ESM simulations for identifying links between extreme weather and aerosol

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

5 TB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Earth System Models NorESM, EC-Earth and ECHAM

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

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Yes

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Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

<https://bolin.su.se/data/>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Nudged ESM simulations

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

We have secure storage located in Sweden, following governmental policies. It is hosted by SUNET and incrementally backed up on a different location.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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